

Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of some novel Mannich's bases of 3-sulfamerazinyl substituted spiro (isatoic anhydrido-4-thiazolidinone) derivatives

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Abstract : Synthesis of novel 3'-[4'-N-{4-methyl-2-pyrimidinyl}-benzene sulphonamido]-spiro-(3*H*-isatoic anhydride-3,2'-thiazolidin)-1*H*-2,4'(5*H*)dione (5) and their Mannich's bases 6(a-g) has been described. Treatment of isatoic anhydride (1) with sulphamerazine (2) yielded 4-[1,2-dihydro-2-oxo-3*H*-isatoic anhydride-3-ylidene]amino]-*N*-(4-methyl-2-pyrimidinyl)benzene sulfonamide (3). Cyclocondensation of its azomethine function with mercaptoacetic acid (4) over basic alumina afforded 3-[4-*N*-{4-methyl-2-pyrimidinyl}-benzene sulphonamido]-spiro-(3*H*-isatoic anhydride-3,2'-thiazolidin)-1*H*-2,4'(5*H*)dione (5) which reacted smoothly with secondary amines and formaldehyde to give Mannich's bases 6(a-g) in excellent yield. Mannich's bases of sulphamerazinyl substituted [spiro-isatoic anhydride-4-thiazolidinone] 6(a-g) were screened for their *in vitro* antimicrobial activities against bacterial species (*E. coli* and *B. subtilis*) and fungal species (*M. phaseolina* and *F. oxysporum*) by agar-well assay method against the standard drugs (ciprofloxacin for bacteria and flucanazol for fungi).

Keywords : Isatoic anhydride, sulphamerazine, mercaptoacetic acid, Mannich's bases.

Introduction

Sulfonamides are well known for their antibacterial¹⁻³, antitumor⁴, diuretic⁵, anticoncarbonic anhydrase^{6,7}, hypoglycemic⁸, antithyroid⁹ and protease inhibiting¹⁰ activities. Isatoic anhydride shows a varying degree of the reactivity of its carbonyl groups towards nucleophilic reagents and this property has been extensively employed in the literature¹¹, in the synthesis of a wide variety of heterocyclic compounds of medicinal interest. Condensed heterocyclic systems containing the thiazolidinone moieties have attracted the attention of the chemists owing to this nuclei having been identified in the literature¹⁵ as the most promising pharmacophores in drug design and synthesis. Spiroheterocyclics containing thiazolidine moiety have been recently shown to exhibit a wide array of interesting biological activities. It has been observed that incorporation of certain bioactive pharmacophores in the existing drug molecules sometimes exert a profound influence on the biological profile of that molecule. Based on these observations, it could be anticipated that incorporation of the bioactive sulphonamide moiety on one side of the spiro-isatoic anhydrido thiazolidinone nucleus and the Mannich's base fragments containing the cyclic

amino methyl group on its other side could produce interesting series of compounds with enhanced biological activity. Ubiquity of thiazolidinones¹⁵, sulphonamides¹⁶ and Mannich's bases¹⁷ in the chemical literature is undoubtedly a consequence of multifarious biological response, which they elicit in combating a variety of body ailments. The recent demonstrations¹⁸ that some of their derivatives can serve as potential agents in the control and treatment of AIDS has stimulated further interest in these molecules from yet another perspective and prompted us to synthesize some novel compounds containing these pharmacophores, on the premise that their presence in tandem in a single molecular framework can contribute significantly to the biological activity in the resulting molecules. As a part of an ongoing endeavour to create novel heterocyclic scaffolds with anticipated biological activity from easily accessible starting materials, herein we report the preliminary results of our studies on the synthesis of the novel 3-sulphamerazinyl substituted tricyclic systems containing spiro-isatoic anhydride-4-thiazolidone nucleus has been identified in the literature¹⁵ as the most promising pharmacophores in drug design and synthesis.

R = (a) Pyrrolidinyl, (b) piperidinyl, (c) morpholinyl, (d) *N*-methyl piperazinyl, (e) *N*-ethyl piperazinyl, (f) *N*-phenyl piperazinyl, (g) *N*-ethoxycarbonyl piperazinyl

Scheme 1

Experimental

Melting points were determined in an open capillary and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded on Shimadzu FTIR-8400S. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ on Bruker DRX-400 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal reference and values are expressed in δ ppm. Purity of all the synthesized compounds were routinely checked by TLC on silica gel G in the solvent system (9 : 1, benzene : methanol).

Synthesis of 3 :

Isatoic anhydride (0.001 mole) **1** and sulphamerazine (0.005 mole) **2** were dissolved in ethanol (10 ml) containing 3 ml of glacial acetic acid the solution was heated under reflux for 12 h and concentrated. The completion of the reaction was checked by TLC. The reaction mixture was cooled in ice water. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with water and recrystallized from aq. ethanol to give **3** (yield 68.9%), m.p. 250–251 °C.

Synthesis of 5 :

Equimolar quantities of **3** (0.001 mole) and mercaptoacetic acid **4** (0.001 mole) were mixed in dry dioxane (10 ml) and the mixture was heated under reflux for 15 h and concentrated. The reaction mixture was cooled and neutralized with 10% sodium bicarbonate solution. The resulting solid was filtered washed with water and recrystallized from dichloromethane and dried to give **5** (yield 70.30%), m.p. 188–189 °C.

General procedure for the synthesis of 6 :

Equimolar quantities of **5** (0.001 mole), pyrrolidine (0.071 g, 0.001 mole) and 37% formaldehyde (0.5 ml) were mixed in dry dioxane (10 ml) and was heated under reflux for 15 h and concentrated. The reaction mixture was cooled and neutralized with 10% sodium bicarbonate solution. The resulting solid was filtered washed with water and recrystallized from dichloromethane and dried to give **6** (yield 71.02%), m.p. 147–148 °C.

Similarly, compounds **6(b-g)** were prepared.

Antimicrobial activity :

Mannich's bases **6(a-g)** were screened for their *in-vitro* antimicrobial activities against bacterial species (*E. coli* and *B. subtilis*) and fungal species (*M. Phaseolina* and *F. oxysporum*) by disc-diffusion method against the standard drugs (ciprofloxacin for bacteria and fluconazol

for fungi). In antimicrobial study, the stock solutions of standard and test compounds were prepared in CHCl₃ and subsequent dilutions were made with the same solvent. The zone of inhibition and activity index were determined by comparison with the standard drug ciprofloxacin. The outcome of this study is presented in Table 1.

Spectral data of compounds 5 and 6(a-g) :

5 : IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3420 (NH symm. str.), 3150 (aromatic str.), 1730 (C=O), 1650 (C=O, str. amide), 1660 (ring skeletal vib.), 1600 (C=N str.), 1240 (SO₂ symm. str), 1150 (-C-N-str. amides), 1435 (C=C aromatic str.), 900–690 (aromatic C-H str.), 610 (C-S str.), 1210 (C-N); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 11.30 (1H, s, NH), 8.28 (1H, d, CH), 7.98 (2H, d, Ar-H), 7.38 (2H, d, Ar-H), 7.52–6.88 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.43 (1H, d, CH), 4.0 (1H, s, NH), 3.43–3.33 (2H, s, CH₂), 2.35 (3H, s, -CH₃); MS : [m/z] 515 (20%); Anal. Calcd./Found for C₂₃H₂₄N₅O₅S₂ : C, 53.68/53.65; H, 4.70/ 4.73 ; N, 13.61/ 13.58; S, 12.46/12.52.

6a : IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3240 (OH), 2898 (aromatic str.), 1700 (C=O), 1650 (C=O, str. amide), 1590 (ring skeletal vib.), 1595 (C=N str), 1425 (C=C aromatic str.), 1234 (C-O-C), 900–690 (aromatic C-H str.), 610 (C-S-C), 1115 (C-N); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 8.28 (1H, d, CH), 7.90 (2H, d, CH₂), 7.38 (2H, d, CH₂), 7.11–6.98 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.35 (1H, d, CH), 4.0 (1H, s, NH), 4.45 (2H, s, N-CH₂-N), 3.43 (2H, s, CH₂), 2.35 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.25 (4H, t, N-(CH₂)₂); MS : [m/z] 613 (20%); Anal. Calcd./Found for C₂₉H₃₆N₆O₅S₂ : C, 56.84/56.92; H, 5.92/5.99 ; N, 13.71/13.65; S, 10.47/10.52.

6b : IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3390 (NH str.), 3050 (C-H str.), 1710 (C=O), 1665 (C=O str.), 1652 (C=N str.), 1234 (SO₂ symm. str.), 1425 (C=C str.), 900–690 (C-H str.), 610 (C-S-C str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 8.28 (1H, d, CH), 7.98 (2H, d, Ar-H), 7.38 (2H, d, Ar-H), 7.11–6.98 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.43 (1H, d, CH), 4.0 (1H, s, NH), 4.45 (2H, s, N-CH₂-N), 3.43–3.33 (2H, s, CH₂), 2.35 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.24 (4H, t, N-(CH₂)₂), 1.50 (6H, t, CH); MS : [m/z] 627 (20%); Anal. Calcd./Found for C₃₀H₃₈N₆O₅S₂ : C, 57.49/57.45; H, 6.11/6.16 ; N, 13.41/13.38; S, 10.23/ 10.28.

6c : IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3390 (NH str.), 3150 (aromatic str.), 1720 (C=O), 1675 (C=O), 1602 (C=N str.), 1425

Table 1. Antimicrobial activity of compounds **6(a-g)**

Compd.	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	<i>E. coli</i>		<i>B. subtilis</i>		<i>M. phaseolina</i>		<i>F. oxysporum</i>	
		A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B
6a	400	20	71.42	27	90.00	19	73.07	18	62.06
	200	14	63.64	18	78.26	13	65.00	13	56.52
	100	9	56.25	11.5	67.64	8.5	56.67	9	50.00
6b	400	25	89.28	25	83.33	16.5	63.46	16	55.17
	200	17	77.27	17	73.91	11.5	57.50	11	47.82
	100	11.5	71.80	11	64.70	7.5	50.00	8	44.44
6c	400	21	75.00	20	66.67	13.5	51.92	23	79.31
	200	15	68.18	13	56.52	9.5	47.50	16	69.56
	100	9	56.25	9	52.94	6.5	43.33	11	61.11
6d	400	19	67.85	21	70.00	17	65.38	21	72.14
	200	14	63.64	14	60.86	12	60.00	14	60.86
	100	9.5	59.30	10	58.82	8	53.33	10	55.56
6e	400	16	57.14	22	73.33	21	80.76	20	68.96
	200	12	54.55	15	62.21	14	70.00	13	56.52
	100	8	50.00	9	52.94	9.5	63.33	9.5	52.78
6f	400	24	85.71	16	53.3	18	69.23	24	82.75
	200	16	72.72	11	47.82	12	60.00	17	73.91
	100	10	62.50	7	41.17	8	53.33	11.5	63.88
6g	400	12	46.15	20	66.67	22.0	78.57	28.0	93.33
	200	11.7	45.0	13	56.52	21.5	76.78	27.6	92.0
	100	10.2	39.23	9	52.94	20.2	72.14	26.2	87.33
Ciprofloxacin	400	28	100	30	100				
	200	22	100	23	100	-	-	-	-
	100	16	100	17	100				
Fluconazole	400					26	100	29	100
	200	-	-	-	-	20	100	23	100
	100					15	100	18	100

(C=C aromatic str.), 1225 (C-O-C), 1160 (SO₂ symm. str.), 900–690 (C-H str.), 610 (C-S-C str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃); δ : 8.28 (1H, d, CH), 7.98 (2H, d, Ar-H), 7.38 (2H, d, Ar-H), 7.11–6.98 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.43 (1H, d, CH), 4.0 (1H, s, NH), 4.45 (2H, s, N-CH₂-N), 3.44–3.33 (2H, s, CH₂), 2.35 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.37 (4H, t, N-(CH₂)₂), 3.67 (4H, t, CH₂); MS : [*m/z*] 629 (20%); Anal. Calcd./Found for C₂₉H₃₆N₆O₆S₂ : C, 55.40/55.35; H, 5.77/5.74; N, 13.37/13.30; S, 10.20/10.22.

6d : IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3390 (NH str.), 3050 (aromatic str.), 1710 (C=O), 1675 (C=O) [CONH], 1602 (C=N str.), 1425 (C=C aromatic str.), 1160 (SO₂ symm. str.), 900–690 (C-H str.), 710 (C-S-C str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃); δ : 8.28 (1H, d, CH), 7.98 (2H, d, Ar-H), 7.38 (2H, d, Ar-H), 7.11–6.98 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.43 (1H, d, CH), 4.0

(1H, s, NH), 4.45 (2H, s, N-CH₂-N), 3.44–3.33 (2H, s, CH₂), 2.35 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.46 (8H, m, N-(CH₂)₄-N), 2.27 (3H, s, CH₃); MS : [*m/z*] 642 (20%); Anal. Calcd./Found for C₃₀H₃₉N₇O₅S₂ : C, 56.14/54.17; H, 6.12/6.16; N, 15.28/15.22; S, 9.99/9.94.

6e : IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3390 (NH str.), 3050 (aromatic str.), 1710 (C=O), 1675 (C=O), 1602 (C=N str.), 1425 (C=C aromatic str.), 1160 (SO₂ symm. str.), 900–690 (aromatic C-H str.), 710 (C-S-C str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃); δ : 8.28 (1H, d, CH), 7.98 (2H, d, Ar-H), 7.38 (2H, d, Ar-H), 7.11–6.98 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.43 (1H, d, CH), 4.0 (1H, s, NH), 4.45 (2H, s, N-CH₂-N), 3.44–3.33 (2H, s, CH₂), 2.35 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.46 (8H, m, N-(CH₂)₄-N), 2.40 (2H, q, CH₂), 1.00 (3H, t, CH₃), 3.5 (2H, q, CH₂); MS : [*m/z*] 656 (20%); Anal. Calcd./Found for

$C_{31}H_{41}N_7O_5S_2$: C, 56.77/56.73; H, 6.30/6.35; N, 14.95/14.92; S, 9.78/9.72.

6f : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3300 (NH str.), 3050 (aromatic str.), 1710 (C=O), 1675 (C=O), 1602 (C=N str.), 1425 (C=C aromatic str.), 1338 (SO₂ symm. str.), 900–690 (C-H str.), 748 (C-S-C str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃), δ : 8.28 (1H, d, CH), 7.88 (2H, d, Ar-H), 7.38 (2H, d, Ar-H), 7.11–6.98 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.43 (1H, d, pyrimidine ring), 4.0 (1H, s, NH), 4.45 (2H, s, N-CH₂-N), 3.45 (4H, t, N-CH₂), 3.44–3.33 (2H, s, CH₂), 2.59 (4H, t, N(-CH₂)₂), 2.35 (3H, s, CH₃); MS : [*m/z*] 704 (20%); Anal. Calcd./Found for $C_{35}H_{41}N_7O_5S_2$: C, 59.72/59.75; H, 5.87/5.89; N, 13.93/13.90; S, 9.11/9.14.

6g : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3410 (NH str.), 3050 (aromatic str.), 1710 (C=O), 1730 (C=O), 1675 (C=O), 1602 (C=N str.), 1425 (C=C str.), 1320 (SO₂ symm. str.), 900–690 (C-H str.), 748 (C-S-C str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 8.28 (1H, d, CH), 7.98 (2H, d, Ar-H), 7.38 (2H, d, Ar-H), 7.11–6.98 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.43 (1H, d, CH), 4.0 (1H, s, NH), 4.45 (2H, s, N-CH₂-N), 3.44–3.33 (2H, s, CH₂), 3.06 (4H, t, N(-CH₂)₂), 2.35 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.62 (4H, t, N(-CH₂)₂), 1.30 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.12 (2H, q, CH₂); MS : [*m/z*] 700 (20%); Anal. Calcd./Found for $C_{32}H_{41}N_7O_7S_2$: C, 54.92/54.95; H, 5.90/5.94; N, 14.01/14.08; S, 9.16/9.12.

Results and discussion

In order for our synthetic plan depicted in Scheme 1 could succeed to give **5** and **6(a-g)**, we required a good synthesis of their precursor **3**. The synthesis of **3** was achieved from isatoic anhydride **1** with sulfamerazine. Literature is replete with examples demonstrating the cyclocondensation of an azomethine function with mercaptoacetic acid to form the 4-thiazolidinone nucleus. This strategy was applied on **3** and **4** to give **5**. When the reaction was carried out on **5**, nitrogen of isatoic anhydride reacted smoothly with formaldehyde and secondary amines viz. pyrrolidine, piperidine, morpholine, 1-methyl piperazine, 1-ethyl piperazine, 1-phenyl piperazine, 1-benzyl piperazine and 1-ethoxy carbonyl piperazine conventionally to give **6(a-g)** (Scheme 1) in excellent yield.

The structure of compounds **3**, **5** and **6(a-g)** were established on the basis of their microanalysis IR, ¹H NMR and MS spectral data. The data shown in experimental section were found in good agreement to the assigned structures.

All compounds gave satisfactory results of their elemental analysis. The spectral data (IR, ¹H NMR and MS) were found to be consistent to the assigned structures.

The antibacterial screening against *E. coli* showed that amongst the compounds **6(a-g)** the compound **6b** displayed highest activity. The compound **6g** showed minimum activity amongst these compounds. Compounds **6a**, **6c**, **6d**, **6e** and **6f** showed only moderate activity. Contrary to this observation, compound **6a** showed highest activity and compound **6f** showed the minimum activity amongst all the compounds screened for antibacterial activity against *B. subtilis*.

The antifungal activity was evaluated against two pathogenic strains (*M. phaseolina* and *F. oxysporum*). The zone of inhibition and activity index were determined by comparison with the standard drug fluconazol. The outcome of this study is presented in Table 1. The antifungal screening against *M. phaseolina* showed that amongst the compounds **6(a-g)**, the compound **6e** exhibited highest activity. The compound **6c** showed minimum activity amongst all the compounds. Compound **6a**, **6b**, **6d**, **6f** and **6g** showed only moderate activity. Contrary to this observation, compound **6g** showed highest activity and compound **6b** the minimum activity amongst all the compounds screened for antifungal activity against *F. oxysporum*.

Conclusion

In conclusion, several novel 3-sulphamerazinyl substituted spiro-isatoic anhydrido-thiazolidinones **6(a-g)** displaying potential antibacterial and antifungal activities were synthesized from the commercially available sulphamerazine, isatoic anhydride and mercaptoacetic acid. The study showed that, it's an elegant method for the synthesis of their Mannich's bases of biological interest.

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